

and those having close values as marked with asterisk are interchangeable) of 1b as portrayed in its structure are in good agreement with the values calculated by using the known additivity parameters of the functional groups on the reported carbon shifts of the 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene⁴. The observed downfield shift of C-3 and C-4 by ~9 ppm is characteristic⁵ of adjacent aromatic carbons bearing oxygen functions. The downfield shift of C-5 by ~9 ppm may be attributed to the proximity of the C-4 methoxyl group. This constitutes the first report of the application of ¹³C-nmr spectroscopy in the structure elucidation of the naturally occurring 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene derivative and the diagnostic features that are revealed may be used for future structural studies of this group of natural products.

Acknowledgement

We thank Dr. B. C. Das, Institut de Chimie des Substances Naturelles, Gif-sur-Yvette, France for the mass spectra and Professor E. Wenkert, Rice University, U.S.A. for the ¹³C-nmr spectra. (S.L.) is thankful to U.G.C., India for financial assistance.

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O-(*N*- α -Pyrrolideneimino)Benzene Sulphonic Acid as an Analytical Reagent for Estimation of V(V)

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Manuscript received 27 October 1980, revised 1 June 1981,
accepted 15 July 1981

A number of organic reagents^{1,2} have been suggested for gravimetric estimation of vanadium(V). The present work is undertaken with the aim to introduce a new reagent, *o*-(*N*- α -Pyrrolideneimino)-benzene sulphonic acid (H_2PB), for gravimetric

estimation of vanadium(V). The vanadium(V)-complex is insoluble in water and can form the basis of a quantitative separation procedure. H_2PB , prepared by the method already reported^{3,4}, (m.p. 172°) gives a rose red precipitate with V(V) in the pH range 3.2-4.0.

Experimental

1% ethanolic solution of H_2PB was used as the reagent. VO_2NO_3 was standardised gravimetrically⁵. All chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Determination of vanadium(V): An aliquot of the vanadium solution [25 to 55 mg of V(V)] was diluted to about 125 ml with distilled water, pH was adjusted between 3.2-4.0 with $HClO_4$ and NH_4OH and heated at 40°-50°. The reagent solution was added gradually with stirring till precipitation completed. It was heated on a water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr and allowed to stand for 2-3 hrs when a granular precipitate formed. It was filtered through a weighed sintered-glass crucible (porosity 4), washed successively with warm water and 10% alcohol until free from the reagent. The complex was dried to a constant weight at 100-110° in a vacuum desiccator, cooled and weighed as $[VO_2 \cdot (C_{11}H_8N_2SO_3)(H_2O)]$. The operation was repeated several times using different quantities of V(V) solutions and results obtained are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF VANADIUM

Wt. of complex (mg)	Vanadium (mg)		Error %
	Calcd.	Found	
181.6	26.53	26.45	-0.30
241.0	35.21	35.14	-0.19
279.4	40.82	40.92	+0.24
306.5	44.78	44.69	-0.20
340.7	49.78	49.89	+0.22

The complex was soluble in concentrated mineral acids, alkalis, dioxan and DMF.

The thermogravimetric analysis of the precipitate indicated a weight loss at 120°-180° corresponding to a water molecule. On further heating a gradual loss in weight due to slow decomposition of the complex was observed. On heating between 380-440°, a sudden loss in weight was recorded and V_2O_5 obtained as the end product.

Effect of foreign ions: In order to assess possible analytical applications of the reagent effect of some ions which often accompanied vanadium was studied.

The interference due to salts of foreign ions was removed in most of the cases by working at controlled pH. In V(V) determination in the pH range 3.2-4.0, anions like CH_3COO^- , Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- and SO_4^{2-} did not interfere.

For 0.1 mg of V(V) solution, the tolerance limit was 25 mg for Be(II), Mn(II), Co(II), Cr(II), Cd(II), Zn(II); 10-15 mg for U(VI), Zr(IV), Th(IV) and Sc(III) and 5 mg for Pt(IV). The Fe(III), Ni(II)

and Cu(II) ions were found to interfere. The interference of Fe(III) was removed by adding tartarate.

Separation and determination of Cu(II), Ni(II) and V(V): A mixture consisting of Cu(II), Ni(II) and V(V) was diluted to 150 ml and its pH was adjusted with HClO₄ and NH₄OH between 2.2-2.4. The solution was heated between 40-50° and 1% ethanolic reagent solution was added. A blue ppt of Cu(II) complex appeared and it was digested on a water-bath between 70-80° for ½ hr. It was then filtered through a weighed sintered-glass crucible and washed with warm water. Finally it was washed with 10% ethanol and dried between 100-110° to a constant weight. The ppt was found to possess the composition [Cu(C₁₁H₈N₂SO₃)(H₂O)₃]. The washings and filtrate were collected and Ni(II) was precipitated between the pH 2.5-3.1 as in the case of Cu(II) complex. The Ni(II) complex possessed the composition [Ni(C₁₁H₈N₂SO₃)(H₂O)₃]. Finally in the filtrate of washings of Ni(II) estimation, V(V) was determined as described earlier.

Estimation of V(V) in ferro-vanadium alloy: A ferro-vanadium alloy containing 35-80% of vanadium was used. A known weight of the alloy was dissolved in conc. H₂SO₄. The solution contained ions like As, Sb, Mo, Fe, W, CrO₄²⁻ and PO₄³⁻ which interfere (W and PO₄³⁻ ion do not interfere) in the quantitative estimation of V(V).

Vanadium was separated and estimated from these ions as follows. The sulphuric acid solution of the alloy was neutralised, rendered faintly acidic and an excess of sulphurous acid added. CO₂ was passed to remove excess of SO₂. H₂S was then passed to precipitate out As₂S₃ and Sb₂S₃. Molybdenum was also removed by passing H₂S under pressure. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness, the residue extracted with water and SO₂ gas was passed until chromium was reduced to trivalent, iron to bivalent while vanadium to tetravalent states. Cr(III) was precipitated out by 10% NaOH solution and removed. The filtrate was treated with 30% H₂O₂ which oxidised Fe(II) to Fe(III) and V(IV) to V(V). Addition of 10% NaOH to this solution precipitated Fe(OH)₃ which was washed with 1% Na₂CO₃ and the washing added to the original filtrate containing vanadium. The process of precipitation of iron was repeated till it was free from vanadium. All the filtrates and washings were collected in which V(V) was estimated by H₂PB in pH 3.2-4.0 as described and weighed as VO₂(C₁₁H₈N₂SO₃)(H₂O).

Elemental analysis and molecular weight of the V(V) complex (337) determined ebulliometrically by Gallenkamp semi micro ebulliometer in dioxane gave its composition as [VO₂(C₁₁H₈N₂SO₃)(H₂O)] having 1:1 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry. It was found diamagnetic. The molecular weight suggests its monomeric nature.

In the ir spectra of H₂PB three bands were observed at 3200 cm⁻¹, 1610 cm⁻¹ and 1180 cm⁻¹ assignable to ν_{NH}, ν_{C-N} and ν_{as}(SO₃H) respectively.

The absence of ν_{NH} in the V(V) complex indicates the involvement of imino nitrogen in chelate formation. The band at 1180 cm⁻¹ also disappeared suggesting coordination through the sulphonate group. ν_{C-N} of H₂PB around 1610 cm⁻¹ was shifted to lower frequency side (1580 cm⁻¹) on chelation indicating the participation of azomethine nitrogen in coordination. The appearance of two new bands in the region 595 cm⁻¹ and 510 cm⁻¹ in the V(V) complex may reflect the M-O and M-N bands. The V(V) complex also exhibits a broad band around 3430-3400 cm⁻¹ due to ν_{OH} of water.

The deprotonated ligand forms a stable chelate with V(V) involving two chelate rings of which one is five-membered and the other six-membered. Thus due to its higher stability the complex becomes totally insoluble.

The structures of the ligand and its V(V) complex are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Vanadium (V) complex of *o*-(*N*- α -Pyrrolideneimino) Benzene Sulphonic Acid.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to CSIR, New Delhi, for the award of Post-doctoral Fellow and Senior Research Fellowship to (C. P. G.) and (K. G. S.) respectively.

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Iodometric Determination of Milligram Amounts of Semicarbazide Hydrochloride by Hypiodite Oxidation

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Manuscript received 9 September 1980, revised 13 March 1981,
accepted 9 June 1981

A simple, rapid and accurate method for the determination of semicarbazide hydrochloride based on its oxidation with sodium hypiodite is described. The procedure can be applied for evaluating 1-20 mg of semicarbazide with an accuracy